

Knowing, doing and showing

A framework for evidencing learning design practice

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DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845035>

Some of the challenges facing third space practitioners include role clarity, professional identity, having a voice, demonstrating value, establishing legitimacy and evidencing expertise. This session focused on the challenge for third space professionals in demonstrating value and evidencing expertise, particularly practitioners in learning design and related roles, and proposed a framework to meet this challenge (Boreland, Henry, & Sharpe, 2025a).

Figure 1: *The Learning Design Evidence Framework*

The framework (Figure 1; Boreland, Henry, & Sharpe, 2025b) aims to guide collection and use of evidence demonstrating impact and efficacy, increasing visibility, justifying funding, supporting career progression and identifying development needs. It is a “fit for purpose” redesign of similar approaches used by academic staff for promotion. The framework was presented for discussion and feedback and provided participants with an opportunity to apply the framework to their own contexts and to plan future actions.

References

- Boreland, J., Henry, T., & Sharpe, S. (2025a). Knowing, doing and showing: a framework for evidencing education and learning designers’ practice in higher education, *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education* (33). <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1210>
- Boreland, J., Henry, T., & Sharpe, S. (2025b). *The Learning Design Evidence Framework* [Figure]. Figshare. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.29993107.v1>

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